

From: editorialservice@peerjournal.org,
To: mattanschlomi@aol.com,
Cc: enzyme@emedscholar.com,
Subject: RE: Resubmit your Articles
Date: Mon, Aug 17, 2020 1:11 pm
Attachments: Enzyme_Engineering_ART_LD.pdf (379K), EEG-20-01_Invoice.pdf (73K)

Dear Dr Schlomi,

Greetings!!

Hope you are doing well.

We would like to inform you that your manuscript "Proteomic Analysis of Autotomy and Regeneration in the Slowpoke Tail" has received positive review comments and with your the acceptance we will go ahead for publication.

In meanwhile we are requesting you to pay the publication charge of \$674 only, so we appeal you to make payment as per the details in invoices

Kindly check the article galley proof

With Best Regards & Thanks

David Brown

Editorial Service Head

Email: editorialservice@peerjournal.org

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From: Mattan Schlomi [mailto:mattanschlomi@aol.com]

Sent: 12 August 2020 14:21

To: editorialservice@peerjournal.org

Subject: Re: Resubmit your Articles

Here you go.

Dr. Mattan Schlomi
mattanschlomi@aol.com

-----Original Message-----

From: Journal Editorial Service <editorialservice@peerjournal.org>

Invoice: EEG-20-01

VAT ID: BE 0719323987

P.O: N/A

Dt: 13 Aug, 2020

Title of the Manuscript	Proteomic Analysis of Autotomy and Regeneration in the Slowpoke Tail
Authors	Mattan Schlomi
Billing Address	Dr. Mattan Schlomi, Japan, Phone : +81 3-3529-1821 Email Id : mattanschlomi@aol.com
Total bill And mode of Payment Or Contact us if you need another mode of transaction We are accepting \$, €, £ currencies.	<p>Publication and manuscript handling cost : Euro 674.00 Total : Euro 674.00 (Six Hundred and Seventy Four Euros Only) Credit Card Payment: We are accepting all major Credit Cards/Debit Cards including AmEx, Visa, MasterCard etc. Please make Online Payment: https://www.longdom.org/onlinepayment/ Pay Publication Fee within one week If you want to send card details please fill the below and send fax to +1-603-758-6903</p> <p>Card type : _____ Card number : _____ Card Holder Name: _____ Expiry Date : _____ CVV Number: _____ Address of card holder : _____</p> <p>Note: While Making Payment through bank ACH/ Wire transfer, it is mandatory to mention invoice number & Journal Name to track your payment.</p> <p>To make Payment in Euros, please use the below account details</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beneficiary's Name: LONGDOM GROUP SA. • Bank Name Address: BNP PARIBAS FORTIS, NV, Montagne DU Parc/warandebg 3, B-1000 Brussels • IBAN NUMBER : BE69001855724578 • Beneficiary's Account No: 001855724578 • BIC CODE: GEBABEBB • Beneficiary's Address: Avenue Roger Vandendriessche 18, 1150 Brussels

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